

INFLUENCE OF INTERNET GAMES ON YOUNG PEOPLE'S MIND
AND ITS NEGATIVE ASPECTS

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Abstract: This article talks about the impact and negative aspects of internet games that have entered our lives and society on the minds of young people.

Key words: internet, electronic games, mass culture, game, social networks, computer games.

Internet is the need of the hour. He is a part of our life it is not a secret to us. Despite the fact that the Internet has many advantages for us there are also negative aspects. It is necessary for us while making our distance close to us allows you to easily find all the information. How from the internet and use is in our hands. Nowadays, the Internet is used for various purposes are using. Virtual video games on the Internet have an impact on young people at the same time, it damages their spiritual consciousness and psyche. The American Medical Association intends to officially list addiction to video games as a mental retardation. According to doctors, this disease threatens the health of anyone who plays games for more than two to three hours a day. This also applies to those who seek happiness on the Internet. The growing popularity of computer games and their negative effects on young people have long been a concern of medical professionals is one of the upcoming problems.

Now there are special hospitals that treat Internet addiction in many regions of the world, including European countries. We found it permissible to mention the events that took place in Korea and European countries as an example. It's a game of addiction; a person begins to learn not real life, but virtual life, and this is known to everyone that a person cannot be ready for any shock. The shrinking of the human mind makes him look at life in a different way, as if he lives alone in life, these games seem like his friends. Unfortunately, people call this game from this trial life, Those who have closed their eyes are also being found more and more. For example; In 2002, a 21-year-old American named Sean Willey shot himself in the forehead. It turned out that he went to the computer game called "EverQuest". He lost that game and collected it turned out that he could not bear to be separated from his points and awards and committed suicide. Unfortunately, these situations also happen in our country. Nowadays, the most

popular game in Uzbekistan is PUBG, currently 60-70% of young people have personal accounts, and anyone without their protection system can hack into this system. And the consequences of this will not lead to good. Half of the 12-16-year-old teenagers who took part in a social survey conducted in Uzbekistan often prefer to chat with their peers and play computer games. 43.7 percent of teenagers limit themselves to reading educational literature. It is known that 1 out of 10 children does not read books other than educational literature. It was reported in the news that a 15-year-old boy stabbed his mother to death in Russia. We see that the mother told her to teach her child without playing a lot of computer games. We don't know when virtual games poisoned our minds.

Therefore, it is very important to properly organize the education process, to constantly monitor the child's upbringing. It is impossible to completely restrict the Internet to a child.

It is natural for a child to become interested in something forbidden. A variety of computer games, i.e. "action", "strategy" or "shooter" from a number of games. It is important to learn how to use it. In other words, the global network of the Internet entered the life of mankind not for entertainment by playing some games, but for the purpose of creating an opportunity to receive scientific information and information that serves the development of science.

In fact, the child's physiological and mental development directly depends on the educational process. Parents are obliged to carry out this process responsibly and seriously. It is important not to let online games that kill people and have fun take the place of national toys, which have always played an important role in the education of children, serve to form their worldview, and direct the criterion of activity to goodness. need It is known that a growing child, being innocent, does not expect evil from the person in front of him. In the same way, it does not occur to him that games that are fun for a child can have negative consequences. It is the indispensable duty of parents and pedagogues to society to teach them to be alert, to conduct explanatory work, and most importantly, to prevent them from falling into the mire of ignorance to the extent that they fall in love with things that look beautiful to their eyes.

The family is the first school in the upbringing of a perfect generation. Teaching a child not to tell lies, to think correctly, to use everything correctly, and to form feelings of love for the Motherland is first carried out in the family. We should not allow our children to control the Internet. Therefore, we are all equally responsible for teaching our children to pay attention to the essence, not the external side of what seems beautiful to their eyes, and to protect them from falling into the disease of "playfulness".

Many games are built on the basis of scenes of brutal killing of people and animals and bloodshed. Such sad pictures have a strong negative impact not only on the minds of young people, but also on the minds of the elderly. The fact that some of those who played games like "GTA", "Sniper", "Killer" and others later became real killers is a clear proof of our opinion.

In addition, we often hear through the mass media: schoolchildren and teenagers in Western countries are causing the death of their parents, teachers, and peers. It is a bitter truth that such terrible events are the poisonous fruit of the "education" that Western children are given in the virtual world. Immersion in futile and harmful activities such as computer games is condemned by Islam. Because as a result, the child's faith weakens, he becomes a slave of the devil and works according to his tricks. As a result, he himself will die. Therefore, we should think about it and think about it.

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